

A Study on Promotional Strategies of XIAOMI in Indian Mobile Industry

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Abstract

Xiaomi is one of the leading company in China. It has been one of the biggest manufacturers in the Smartphone market .it's a privately owned Chinese electronics design and manufacturing company. Founded by Lei Jun in 2010, the company has its headquarters in Beijing and comes about the fourth on the list of the top Smartphone makers in the world. Xiaomi introduced the Redmi series which gave competition to many mobile phones like Samsung, Motorola and Lenovo budget oriented phones. Xiaomi flagship phone is also the reason for their popularity. Since From past 2 years Chinese mobile company Xiaomi mobile price covered the biggest 30 cities in India then Xiaomi becomes the second largest selling mobile company in India. Xiaomi becomes a second largest position with 30% market share of the Indian market. Xiaomi has the best quality mobile with low price and Camera of Xiaomi became a competition with oppo and vivo. The company offers good specification at a low price. Even though at a low priced rate mi provides the best quality product. Xiaomi phones become more popular in the short term. Xiaomi introduced many series of Mi that is redmi note 4; redmi note 5 and redmi note 5 pro become more popular nowadays. The company largely sells its Xiaomi Redmi, Xiaomi Note, Xiaomi Mi Note Pro, and other series of smart phones via flash sales in India. All the most recent Xiaomi mobiles are equipped with the latest features and specifications. Xiaomi mobiles are perfect for those who are looking for the latest technology, advanced features, and attractive design at an affordable price .the research paper is all about further analysis on the marketing strategies of Xiaomi mobile phone currently used, the establishment and implementation of the whole marketing the system of Xiaomi mobile phone which is expounded in six aspects with the Advertising strategy, promotion strategy, online promotional distribution strategy, product strategy, pricing strategy and channel strategy. One of the core content of marketing strategy is 4P theory where the company focus on product and its pricing strategies along with the appropriate promotion strategy and its implementation.

Keywords: Affordable Price, Latest Technology, Advertising Strategy, and 4p's Theory.

Introduction:

Xiaomi has been one of the biggest manufacturers in the Smartphone market in China. The company has many products, it produces Smartphones which run on their own version of android MIUI firmware. Their brand is Redmi, where "MI" stands for **mobile internet**. It is the brilliant idea by the serial entrepreneur Lei Jun in the year 2010. This private Chinese electronics company headquartered in Beijing, China. Xiaomi company is the 4th largest Smartphone maker. The company largely sells its Xiaomi Redmi, Xiaomi Note, Xiaomi Mi Note Pro, and other series of Smartphones via flash sales in India. All the most recent Xiaomi mobiles are equipped with the latest features and specifications. Xiaomi mobiles are perfect for those who are looking for the latest technology, advanced features, and attractive design at an affordable price. Xiaomi phones in India are perfect for people who cater to both personal and professional usage. It has managed to rank along and give a neck-to-neck competition to high-end smart phones from the Samsung mobile price list, Apple mobile price list, etc. Xiaomi mobiles come with excellent cameras along with a large storage and memory capacities. Smartphones from this brand are sleek and fit the palm perfectly. The phones are designed with features like Full HD display, front and rear cameras, dual SIM and a built-in storage system. As far as the battery of the mobiles is concerned, the Xiaomi phones in India are competent to run through the entire day. Interestingly, Xiaomi is the leading Smartphone brand in India. The brand has Smartphones in a wide price range that can fit all budget requirements. You can look for an affordable high-end or affordable Xiaomi phone depending on your budget and requirements. The Redmi mobile price list comprises of the affordable Smartphones under the brand.

Reason behind Xiaomi's success is targeted marketing. They targeted common people of India which makes 70% of India's population.

- Xiaomi's pricing was best they priced very competitively such that other Chinese brands were just out of that game. Big players like Samsung always ignored their budget segment so Xiaomi pounced on this opportunity.
- Xiaomi provided best budget hardware and software experience to users which made them obvious favourites.
- Questions come how Xiaomi can afford such cheap products with good specs answer is big companies like Google, Samsung, Apple spend tons of money on Research & Development. Xiaomi uses existing parts and come up with the nice phone.
- Xiaomi also uses flash sale which some people don't like but this strategy helps them to manufacture the right amount of phones and they don't run into losses.
- Price, the first reason people chose Mi is its cheap price for better quality products. Quality, yes even though very cheap rate Mi provides better quality products, for same in other company you need to pay more for the same quality product.
- Service, even though the very large number of customer Mi take care all of them very effectively. Their service centre take care by top-level management so that would be one of the reasons.

Objective of the study

1. To study the sales promotion mix of Xiaomi
2. To find out the marketing Strategies of the brand.

Research methodology

This is the conceptual research paper analysing the sales promotion of xiamoi by relating the paper with the 4p theory of marketing and by analysing the swot analysis of the company and also the sales analysis of xiaomi has been considered n this paper

One of the core content of marketing strategy is **4P theory** where the company focus on product and its pricing strategies along with the appropriate promotion strategy and its implementation.

Product

- Smart home devices
- Smartphone & Mobile phones
- Laptops
- Tablet computers

The use of Facebook by Xiaomi to communicate to users on a regular basis, with the aim of getting feedbacks, has played an important role in the development of new products that would meet the consumer needs. Such use of social media positions Xiaomi as a unique company as very few other companies in the world do such a thing. In other words, the company is more consumers' oriented

Price

Most of the money spent on Xiaomi products are strictly spent on design and production. The company tries to save as much as it can, thus offering products to the market at an affordable rate. In other words, on average, Xiaomi products are lowly priced. The company mainly employs marketing strategies that don't cost a lot. In addition, most of the products are sold online thus reducing the cost that would have been spent to set up offline stores. The company employs a pricing strategy that will help them get profits in the future. It is a sell-low-today but gains later strategy. They, therefore, sell their devices at the exact cost that only covers production costs. Their profit generation focus is on the accessories, apps, and services that are to be used with their phones and computers etc. Xiaomi has proven that cheap pricing doesn't always mean cheap products.

Place

Xiaomi is Chinese company but for a wider market than just China. However, its strong base is within its Homeland-China. As at now, the company is also emerging in 11 other countries. These include Turkey, Malaysia, Mexico, Thailand, Philippines, Russia, Singapore, Indonesia, Brazil, India, and Vietnam, with most of the countries being found in the BRIC and South East Asia regions. In spite of it trying to go international, Xiaomi's main focus is

still in China as this is where it already has a formidable consumer base. Most of Xiaomi's sales are done online rather than on the physical stores. As a result, a win-win situation is realised by both the manufacturer and the consumer. The company saves lots of money from building and managing stores as customers easily access products without having to pay the distributor, wholesaler, and retailer.

Promotion

Xiaomi is an active use of the social media among other marketing channels to not only broadcast their messages and agenda but also to actively get and remain in touch with their customers as well as potential customers. The company's engineers also make good use of the social media especially Facebook, to routinely communicate to users for feedback. Such feedbacks are used in the development of new products. The use of flash sales helps the company to sell to sell their Smartphone's and other products in limited numbers and within very limited time periods. This is an important sales strategy that enables the company to save money that would have been used in advertisements as the strategy does create urgency and anticipation on consumers. Just a limited number of products are produced and sold quite fast thus making others to wait for the next batch. The wait is always with a lot of anticipation and urgency. Many [people](#) end up talking especially on social media thus unknowingly promoting Xiaomi products .Xiaomi has a very big and formidable fan base that has successfully been able to show their support for the Xiaomi products. These are fans that are always present whenever a new [product](#) is being launched. The presence of such a fan base alone is enough applause and noise to attract the attention of potential customers.

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS

- One of the Largest Smartphone makers – Xiaomi is one of the largest smart phone makers in the world. It is said to be the 5th largest Smartphone manufacturer as of 2017. Originating from China, the Smart phones are manufactured in huge quantities and have wide acceptance across the world.
- Highest selling Smartphone – The REDMI Note 4 became the highest selling smart phone in India and China and practically in 50% of the Asian market. This shows that Xiaomi is strongly rising in the smart phone market and has already beaten several giants
- Huge China and Asia market available – Another benefit to Xiaomi is that the whole Asian market is their playground. As China lies within Asia and as Chinese mobile brands are highly penetrated in the Asian markets, Xiaomi still has a lot of ground to explore.
- Penetration Pricing – Xiaomi has the strongest penetration pricing advantage because it generally uses direct marketing techniques and avoids dealer and distributor margins

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- Good Quality products – Even at such low prices, no one can doubt the quality of Xiaomi phones. The smart phones are regularly rated high on all E-commerce portals – a further proof that Xiaomi does not compromise on quality even if lowers the price regularly.
 - Manufacturing Advantage – China has a huge manufacturing advantage because the country in itself is known for manufacturing and exporting the products. China is also one of the largest consumers in the Asian market.
 - Specifications of the smartphones produced– Xiaomi smart phones are technologically advanced as well and they give higher tech specs at lower price. Xiaomi phones are especially renowned for their camera which is said to be very high resolution and gives excellent photos.
 - Research and Development – Xiaomi invests heavily in Research &Development and it is a market follower but its major R&D expenses are towards cost advantage and not differentiation advantage

WEAKNESSES

- **Offline Distribution** – Xiaomi mainly sold through the flash sale but at times, it was difficult for customers to get their hands on a REDMI or MI model phone. This is because their offline distribution is not up to mark and Xiaomi phones sell mainly via E-commerce.
- **Advertising and Marketing spends** – The advertising and marketing spends of the brand is very low. The brand launches ATL campaigns only when coming up with a new product. However, the advertising is erratic at best and is never consistent.
- **Low Skimming price** – While other Smartphone manufacturers survive on skimming price, Xiaomi launches its own phones at low prices in the flash sales. As a result, it cannot take advantage of the skimming price or the advantage is not as profitable as it would be for Samsung or Apple or other such high end brands.

OPPORTUNITIES

- **Expansion** – Covering the developing countries and the emerging markets should be the priority for Xiaomi. As it mainly follows online sales model, which is becoming popular in many countries, it should expand to countries where E-commerce mode of purchase is well established or in the process of establishment.
- **Distribution** – Besides online distribution, Xiaomi also needs to concentrate on offline distribution if it ever wants to be consistent like some of its top competitors.

Offline distribution would also mean higher expenses and therefore a rise in price. But it will help the brand to create a long term image and equity.

- **Brand Building** – Brand building methods such as Sales promotions, Trade promotions, ATL campaigns and BTL campaigns should be launched as regularly as possible to build a better brand image. Xiaomi is far behind Oppo and Vivo where BTL Campaigns are concerned.
- **Penetration of Smartphone's** – Across the world, the smart phone as a product is being adopted and people are using more and more Smartphone's with combination of Internet. This market penetration of Smartphone is for the benefit of Xiaomi. The better phones they manufacture, the more they will be able to capture the market share.
- **Product innovations & Differentiation** – Being a market follower is tough and Xiaomi needs to get a step ahead by introducing highly differentiated phones which have innovative touches to it. Moreover, it needs to advertise these advantages to get more and more customers to buy their products.

THREATS

- **Competition** – Oppo and Vivo are 2 of the biggest competitor for Xiaomi because they are themselves from China and have the same manufacturing advantages like Xiaomi. Besides this, Oppo and Vivo have a strong offline presence and have huge distribution network. Thus, they are a huge threat to Xiaomi.
- **Service** – The lack of service centres equivalent to the number of sales by the brand is a worrying statistic. Xiaomi needs to increase its sales and service centres both if it wants to retain its customers.

Brand Differentiation is absent – The smart phone segment has become such that brand differentiation is becoming very difficult. Each brand is coming up with products which are almost similar, thereby making it difficult for the customer to choose one brand over other. This will become especially difficult when more and more brands come from China.

SALES ANALYSIS OF XIAOMI

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